

ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNITY PERCEPTIONS AND PRACTICES REGARDING PREVENTION OF DENGUE FEVER

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Abstract

Objectives: To assess knowledge, attitude and practices of health care seekers regarding dengue prevention and control.

Methodology: Cross sectional study. Study Area: Study has been conducted in government health care facilities of primary and secondary level in district Rawalpindi. Study Period: Study has been conducted during a period of 6 months from March 2019 to Sept 2019. Study Population: Community members visiting the health care facility for reasons other than dengue fever. Sampling Technique: Multistage sampling has been used to select the study participants. Source of Data: Primary source of data collection has been used. This data has been collected by face to face interviews with the help of a framed questionnaire. Sample Size: Was calculated using open epi software and came out to be 310. For facility based analysis, total of 31 facilities were recruited including 3 District level hospitals, all RHCs and THQs and 2 BHUs from each tehsil. 10 Community members from each facility were recruited and total community members from 31 facilities were 310. Result: All community participants recruited in the study (100%) knew about the disease but their core knowledge and practices were not good. Majority of them 76.1% know about the disease from their family, friends, neighbors or teachers. Those learn from doctors were 23.9%. Only 1 respondent shared that there is someone infected with the disease in his/her close vicinity that is his/her neighbor/friend and that person immediately contacted health facility for treatment. 41.3% respondents reported using bed nets while 58.7% people had not adopted that protection measure. 40.6% people among 128 participants revealed that they self purchased the bed nets. Only 2(0.6%) said that government provided these bed nets. Moreover, according to 41.3% people recruited in study, bed nets they used were not impregnated. The reasons for not using bed nets include unaffordability (20.3%), hot weather (8.1%), and unpleasant smell (1.9%)

All Community members visited the health facility for the reason other than dengue, among them only 1% witnessed organization of awareness campaigns in their areas by government Health Team. They were also asked to provide some suggestions for dengue prevention and control. Majority (62.6%) suggested keeping environment clean and (9.7%) said to provide proper sanitation facilities, (16%) suggested for proper water drainage, (3.9%) suggested that there should be regular spray, (2.3%) gave importance to the use of bed nets, (0.6%) gave importance to the use of quill and lotion and (4.5%) suggested for the use of safe water.

Conclusion: The knowledge and attitude of the respondents concerning dengue control was not satisfactory, focusing more on the things which are not primarily concerned with dengue and they were giving less importance to the personal protective measures e.g the use of bed nets, use of anti mosquito lotions, use of quills, use of sprays which constitute cornerstone in dengue prevention and control.

Key words:- knowledge, attitude, practice, dengue, Rawalpindi

Dengue fever continues to be a potential public health threat in subtropical and tropical countries for the past decades where 2.5 billion population is at risk of getting disease.¹ It is the most significant challenge, world is facing since 1980s and has become a major public health concern globally with 70% occurrence rate in Asia Pacific alone.¹ In 2012 ranking, dengue fever considered as the most significant vector-borne viral disease having epidemic potential. Besides staggering human and economic

costs, there has been a 30-times rise in disease incidence over the past 50 years. WHO declared dengue fever as the most common arthropod-borne communicable disease caused by four flavivirus serotypes through the transmission by female *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*.² An infected female mosquito can transmit any of the four viral serotypes to susceptible humans in one bite.^{3,4,5} WHO estimates suggest that more than 100 million dengue infections may occur worldwide every year.

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Pakistan ranked sixth among most populous countries with estimated population of 207 million. In recent decades, considerable social changes have led to expeditious urbanization. Economic survey 2014 indicated the estimated nominal per capita GDP of US\$1,197 with 21% of the people subsisting below the international poverty line of US\$1.25 a day. Infectious and contagious diseases pose a heavy burden on the health care system in Pakistan along with having a negative impact on socio-economic growth and productivity.⁶ Among those, dengue is threatening lives of the millions of people because of its predominating distinct socio-economic conditions and definitive epidemiological position. First case of dengue fever was reported in 1985 followed by re-appearance in 1994 and 1995. Pakistan has faced several dengue outbreaks since then, worst being in 2011, costing hundreds of human lives. Dengue cases have been reached to an alarming level especially during post monsoon season and the disease has been declared endemic in Pakistan.⁷ It was reported as an undifferentiated fever first time in 1985 in Pakistan affecting children under 16 years of age.⁸ During the year 1995, 75 new cases of dengue were reported in Hubb, Baluchistan¹ followed by 1000 infections and 7 deaths in Haripur while 2500 cases reported in Khushab, Nowshera with 11 deaths among those infected individuals during the year 2003. In 2004, 25 cases were declared from Karachi and Islamabad while in 2005, 13 patients died out of 500 dengue infected cases in Karachi. The year 2006 brings 5400 dengue cases from Karachi, Sukkar, Nawabshah, Rawalpindi and Islamabad and 55 deaths reported.^{10,11} In 2007, dengue again affected Karachi, Hyderabad, Mirpurkhas, Lahore, Haripur, Rawalpindi and Islamabad, and 2700 cases were highlighted along with 24 deaths. In 2008, there was high frequency of DHF in Lahore with 1800 positive cases for dengue. In 2009, overall 570 cases while in 2010, 5000 positive cases were documented. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Azad Jammu Kashmir, 25 and 5 cases were stated from both areas, respectively. Pakistan had faced the worst outbreak of

dengue in 2011. More than 20,000 people were affected and resulted in 300 deaths according to official reports. Majority of the cases were observed in Lahore followed by other cities of Punjab including Faisalabad, Rawalpindi and Sargodha.¹² In Karachi, Sindh 196 cases were recorded. Various researches have shown that there is a need to give awareness and knowledge to the people of different preventive practices for combating dengue effectively. Television/Radio plays the important role in conveying health information to the population. But due to poor financial condition all cannot buy TV/Radios and newspapers for information so effective campaigns must be done.¹³ The purpose of this study is to assess knowledge, attitude and practices of community regarding dengue prevention and control, Community perception regarding dengue fever and their behavior of adapting general preventive strategies.

METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional study was conducted to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of the community members visiting the government health facilities of primary and secondary level for reasons other than dengue fever at district Rawalpindi during a period of 6 months March 2019 to Sept 2019. Primary source of data collection has been used. This data has been collected by face to face interviews with the help of a framed open ended questionnaire. Sample size was taken as 310 calculated by open epi software at 95% confidence interval and at 5% margin of error, taking frequency of anticipated factor i.e knowledge of dengue among population as 72%.¹⁴ Sampling was done through multistage sampling in which facility based selection was done through stratified sampling technique out of 118 health facilities 31 facilities were recruited including 3 District level hospitals, all RHCs and THQs and 2 BHUs from each tehsil. We selected 10 Community members through simple random sampling from each health care facility and total community members from 31 facilities were 310.

RESULTS

A total of 310 community members were randomly selected and interviewed, who were visiting health facilities for reasons other than dengue. 10 community members were selected from each facility in which both man and women of different age groups were observed visiting health facility. Maximum were females 73.55%(228). Majority of the participants were of the age group 20-50yrs 62.90% (195), while minimum above 50 years of age 4.19%(13). Most of the community participants had matric level education representing 33.55%(104). Only 2.58% had graduate level education.(Table 1). All community participants recruited in the study (100%) knew about this disease. Majority of them 76.1% know about the disease from their family, friends, neighbors or teachers. Those learn from doctors were 23.9%. Only 1 respondent shared that there is someone infected with the disease in his/her close

vicinity that is his/her neighbor/friend and that person immediately contacted health facility for treatment. 41.3% respondents reported using bed nets while 58.7% people had not adopted that protection measure. 40.6% people among 128 participants revealed that they self purchased the bed nets. Only 2(0.6%) said that government provided these bed nets. Moreover, according to 41.3% people recruited in study, bed nets they used were not impregnated. The reasons for not using bed nets include unaffordability (20.3%), hot weather (8.1%), and unpleasant smell (1.9%)(Table 2).

All Community members who visited the health facility for the reason other than dengue only 1% witnessed organization of awareness campaigns in their areas by government Health Team. They were also asked to provide some suggestions for dengue prevention and control. Majority (62.6%) suggested keeping environment clean and (9.7%)

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Community Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (N=310)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	82	26.45
Female	228	73.55
Age Groups (Years)		
15-29	102	32.90
20-50	195	62.90
Above 50	13	4.19
Education		
Not Literate	33	10.64
Under Primary	56	18.06
Under Matric	53	17.09
Matriculate	104	33.55
Intermediate and above	64	20.64
Type of Health Facility		
DHQ	10	3.22
THQ	60	19.35
RHC	80	25.81
BHU	140	45.16
THQ	20	6.44
Respondent by Tehsil		
Gujjar Khan	60	19.35
Kahutta	30	9.68
Kallar Sayean	30	9.68
Kotli Sattian	40	12.90
Murree	40	12.90
Rawalpindi	80	25.81
Taxila	30	9.68

Table 2: Health Care Seekers Awareness Regarding Dengue Prevention and Control

Variables	Awareness	Frequencies	Percentages
Knowledge about disease	YES	310	100
	NO		
Source of information	Peers (Family, Friends, Teacher, Neighbor)	235	76
	Doctor	75	24
Health facility reported in case of illness	Govt. hospitals	90	29
	RHC/BHU/Dispensary	219	70.6
	Private hospitals/clinic	1	0.3
Total		310	100
Adequate treatment provided	YES	280	90
	NO	30	10
Free of cost treatment provided	YES	307	99
	NO	3	1
Use of bed nets	YES	7	2.3
	NO	303	97.7
Reasons for not using bed nets	Affordability	106	35
	Feel heat	75	24.7
	Feel smell	3	1
	Other	119	39.3
Total		303	100
Awareness campaigns held in the community	YES	100	100
	NO	Nil	

said to provide proper sanitation facilities, (16%) suggested for proper water drainage, (3.9%) suggested that there should be regular spray, (2.3%) gave importance to the use of bed nets, (0.6%) gave importance to the use of quill and lotion and (4.5%) suggested for the use of safe water (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

The study has been conducted in district Rawalpindi, located in the northernmost part of the Punjab province of Pakistan. Dengue is major public health concern of this area. The number of patients affected

Table 3: Suggestions for Dengue Prevention and Control

	Fre- quency	Per- cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No Answer	51	16.5	16.5	16.5
Keep clean your place	24	7.7	7.7	24.2
Keep environment neat and clean	194	62.6	62.6	86.8
Need more awareness	3	1	1	87.7
Need proper sanitation	30	9.7	9.7	97.4
Need Sanitation	1	0.3	0.3	97.7
Use quill and lotion	2	0.6	0.6	98.4
Use quile	2	0.6	0.6	99
Use safe water	3	1	1	100
Total	310	100	100	

by dengue virus has reached to an alarming figure of 3600 during 2017. Moreover, six deaths from dengue fever have also been reported in Rawalpindi District.¹⁶

Community members visiting health facilities for reasons other than dengue fever were recruited in the study and majority among them was females. Similar study was conducted in Cambodia in which out of 600 participants who were administered the KAP survey, the majority were female (77.8%),² This is suggestive of health seeking behavior of females because they are a vulnerable group and having a high level of physical, psychological, and/or social risk.

All respondents reported nearby health facility or hospital in their vicinity. Among those facilities, majority were BHU, RHC or Dispensary and according to them patients were provide suitable treat-

ment in those health facilities. Majority of the participants told that these facilities are providing free of cost treatment.

These facilities were in close proximity to the residence of most community participants and it is usually easy for the females to approach these facilities for care seeking. Only small proportion of participants was not literate, otherwise maximum had matric level education. All these were well aware of the disease Majority of them know about the disease from their family, friends, neighbors, teachers or doctors. A sizeable proportion of the respondents were using personal prophylaxis measures against mosquitoes. However, a considerable number was not aware of preventive measures against mosquitoes at community level., this shows there were lack of awareness campaigns to raise the basic awareness level of public knowledge about dengue fever its prevention and control. A KAP survey together with an extensive entomologic survey was conducted in two subdistricts of Kamphaeng Phet province, Thailand.¹⁷ To improve Community knowledge the awareness campaigns must be repeatedly organized by Government. Personal Protection is an important point in prevention from dengue fever as mosquito bite is the cause of disease transmission. In this study people were more focusing on the factors which are not cornerstone in the prevention of dengue fever e.g sanitation, clean environment and safe water supply, and were giving least importance to the personal protection factors that are directly concerned with dengue fever prevention e.g use of bed nets for protection against mosquitoes ,use of quill and lotions ,use of mosquito repellent sprays. It should be noted that people are largely unaware of tires and flower pots as being important breeding places for mosquitoes. Similarly, knowledge and use of interventions Beside poor knowledge about dengue fever some people were not using bed nets because of un-affordability, difficulty in using during summer season because of hot weather and unpleasant smell of these bed nets. These issues must be considered in awareness

campaigns. A study from Brazil on the public knowledge and attitudes concerning dengue found a gap between knowledge and practices about vector prevention.¹⁸ Another study from Northeast Thailand identified several barriers towards dengue control including insufficient control agents and inadequate knowledge of control methods.¹⁹ Swaddiwudhipong W et al have suggested that health education can induce the people to accept themselves as being responsible for Aedes control programs.²⁰ A study done in Puerto Rico regarding attitudes towards dengue prevention revealed that participants insisted that "neighbours" needed to control larval habitats, and the Government had the responsibility to fumigate.²¹

Based on our findings, it is recommended that future campaigns should involve more aggressive health education in cooperation with health workers and community schools. Audiovisual media can also be used as a tool to disseminate mass awareness.²² Health education programmes should, therefore, deliver information in a more compatible socio-cultural context for a friendlier and effective reception.¹⁹ Capacity building is also an essential part for successful community participation.

This study not only provides important basic information among the community regarding dengue prevention and control but can also help to identify areas that can be targeted in future campaigns. The knowledge obtained from this study may can be used to monitor the effectiveness and progress of dengue prevention campaigns.

CONCLUSION

The knowledge and attitude of the respondents concerning dengue control was not satisfactory, people don't know that dengue mosquito bites at day time and breed in clean water. They were focusing more on the things which are not primarily concerned with dengue like sanitation and they were giving less importance to the personal protective measures e.g the use of bed nets, use of anti mosquito lotions, use of quile, use of sprays which constitute

cornerstone in dengue prevention and control. Adequate preventive practices and education can be achieved by improving the knowledge and awareness level of the people, particularly from rural and illiterate background is important. So the awareness educational campaigns should be designed to improve behavior and practices of prevention & control measures against dengue fever of the community.

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WHEN TO USE A MASK

For healthy people wear a mask only if you are taking care of a person with suspected 2019-nCoV infection

Wear a mask, if you are coughing or sneezing

Masks are effective only when used in combination with frequent hand-cleaning with alcohol-based hand rub or soap and water

If you wear a mask then you must know how to use it and dispose of it properly

